

Material Perturbations to Enhance Performance of the Thiele Half-Width Antenna

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Introduction

Microstrip antennas have been shown to radiate when the dominant or fundamental mode is suppressed and the first higher order mode is excited [1]. One such microstrip variation is the Thiele Half-Width (THW) antenna [2], which operates from 5.9 - 8.2 GHz in this paper. Increasing the bandwidth over which the THW antenna operates is desired, as is an increase in the leakage constant, α , over this region. A larger α over the leaky region will allow for the antenna to be shorter in length. This work seeks to vary the material and physical properties of the THW antenna, including strip-width variations, modification of the substrate layer and the addition of a superstrate, to achieve these results.

Leaky Wave Antenna Theory

Microstrip guided-wave structures typically operate in the fundamental mode (the EH_0 mode) which does not radiate (see Figure 1a). However, if the fundamental mode is blocked, the first higher order mode (the EH_1 mode) can radiate and thus, the microstrip can be utilized as a leaky traveling wave antenna [1]. This is due to the phase reversal in the fields at the center of the structure (see Figure 1b) allowing the fields to decouple into the substrate and free space regions. It is this phase reversal at the center of the structure that is the basis for the THW antenna, which adds a shunt longitudinally down the center between the strip and ground-plane conductors to block-out the fundamental mode.

Figure 1a: Electric field distribution of EH_0 mode.

Figure 1b: Electric field distribution of the EH_1 mode

The voltage and current are in phase down the THW antenna, both of the form $e^{-j\gamma z}$, where $\gamma = k_z = \beta - j\alpha$. The value β is called the propagation constant, whereas α is called the leakage constant. A larger α will, in turn, cause more energy to be radiated and less energy to reach the end of the antenna. This will prevent standing waves from forming and will allow for the antenna to operate as a traveling wave, thus increasing its bandwidth. The leaky wave region begins when $\alpha = \beta$ (cutoff frequency) and continues as long as $\beta < k_0$. Above this latter

point in frequency, the antenna no longer radiates, due to coupling into surface-wave modes of the substrate layer. What determines the leakage constant, α , over this region is not fully understood. By using a Transverse Resonance Code (TRC) [3] and a 3-D Finite Difference Time Domain (FDTD) code to look at material and physical variations in the THW antenna, insight will be gained into what affects α and why. This insight will be used to improve the antenna performance.

Physical Variations in THW Antenna

The Transverse Resonance Code (TRC) has been shown to accurately predict the α and β over the leaky region of microstrip antenna structures. Several variations in the width of the top conductor and permittivity of the dielectric slab were made and tested using the TRC. The reflection coefficients (Γ) of the transverse wave under the top conductor at the conductor/slab junction were also computed.

Keeping the height of the THW constant, the width of the antenna was varied. It was observed that as the width of the antenna was increased, the cutoff frequency of the leaky region decreased. The width of the strip is the prime driver for the operating frequency, yet it has no effect on the bandwidth of the antenna. In contrast, as the permittivity of the substrate was decreased, the cutoff frequency of the leaky region increased, as did the bandwidth of the leaky region.

Figure 2: Multiple Leaky Wave Microstrip Antennas.

Several microstrip designs were analyzed using the TRC, all of which having roughly the same cutoff frequency, (see Figure 2) but with different widths and permittivities. It can be seen that as the relative permittivity of the substrate approaches free space ($\epsilon_r=1$), the bandwidth of the leaky region becomes very large but is still finite (not TEM). This is due to the top conductor having a finite

width and, thus, a cutoff frequency. The resultant bandwidths show that as the permittivity is increased and the width is decreased, the bandwidth is decreased over the leaky region. In all cases, the magnitude of the transverse reflection coefficient, Γ , increases linearly from 0.95 to 1.00 across the leaky region and the phase goes to 0° . At this point, the antenna operates in the surface-wave regime.

Material Variations in THW Antenna

A different admittance is seen at the conductor/slab junction looking out into the substrate ($Y_a(\zeta)$) as opposed to the admittance looking back under the top conductor. This difference will lead to a value for Γ that is less than unity [4]:

$$\Gamma = (Y_c - Y_a(\zeta)) / (Y_c + Y_a(\zeta))$$

where $Y_c = (\epsilon_r/\mu_r)^{1/2} (\eta_0)^{-1}$ mhos is the characteristic wave admittance of the TEM wave in a parallel plane waveguide, $Y_a(\zeta) = -i Y_c \tan[X(\zeta)/2]$ is the apparent end-admittance, $\zeta = k_{z\epsilon}/k_0$ is the normalized propagation constant in the z-direction inside the dielectric, $\eta_0 = (\epsilon_0/\mu_0)^{1/2} = 120\pi$ ohms, and $X(\zeta)$ is a obtained from the TRC. Thus, the transverse wave underneath the top conductor can be reflected back under the top conductor at the conductor/slab junction, causing the waves to be longitudinally bound under the top conductor. By varying the permittivity of the substrate underneath the top conductor, these admittances could be "tuned" to allow for the maximum amount of energy to escape transversely and, thus, promote radiation as a leaky wave.

An FDTD simulation was used to investigate whether changing the materials in the THW could be used to lower Γ , thus allowing more energy to escape transversely from under the top conductor. As a basis, the FDTD code used by Zelinski [5] to analyze the THW antenna was modified to allow for variations in the antenna/substrate properties. The code produced the longitudinal α and β values over the frequencies of interest. Several variations were made to the baseline THW antenna, some modifying the substrate under the top conductor (Figure 3a) and others adding a superstrate (Figure 3b).

Figure 3a: Microstrip with Varied ϵ_3 Under Top Conductor.

Figure 3b: Microstrip with Superstrate of Relative Permittivity ϵ_3 .

The results of the FDTD analysis show incremental changes in the bandwidth of the leaky region for the microstrip in Figure 3a. As the permittivity of the substrate outside (ϵ_2) the top conductor is lowered, both the bandwidth and cutoff frequency increase (see Figure 4). An 8.43% bandwidth improvement (above the baseline THW antenna) was obtained by lowering ϵ_2 from 2.33 to 1.03.

Conversely, as the permittivity of ϵ_2 is increased, the bandwidth and cutoff frequency both decrease. For the $\epsilon_2=3.33$ case, the bandwidth decreased 2.67%. For the superstrate test cases, Figure 5 shows the results of the FDTD testing. The addition of a superstrate causes the cutoff frequency of the leaky region to decrease for all cases. For these curves, the bandwidth decreased 7.37% for the $\epsilon_3=1.33$ case, 11.6% for the $\epsilon_3=4.33$ case, and 13.1% for the $\epsilon_3=5.33$ case.

Figure 4: Leaky Microstrip with Varied Material Properties.

Figure 5: Leaky Microstrip with Superstrate.

Summary

The FDTD and Transverse Resonance analyses show that variations in the physical construction of the leaky wave antenna can cause changes in α and β over the leaky region. Further analysis is needed to optimize these values.

References:

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